

ANTHROPONYMOUS UNITS AND THEIR LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS

Yusupova Alfiya Shavketovna

A teacher of Kazan State University.

Hamroyeva Maftuna Rasulovna

A teacher of Bukhara State University.

Abstract. *This article discusses the specific features of personal names in a certain language, their semantic-stylistic functions in a work of art. Also, the semantic function of anthroponyms and their various forms and linguistic importance are discussed.*

Key words: *semantic, stylistic, anthroponyms, form, artistry, artistic work, personal names, meaning, methodology, artistic style, literary language, artistic language, existence, surname, nickname.*

In world linguistics, the second half of the 20th century is characterized by the formation of anthropocentrism as a priority direction in scientific research at the beginning of the 21st century, and increased attention to the study of the human personality in all scientific fields. In particular, in linguistics, such an approach is manifested in the study of the linguistic landscape of the individual and the world. In this regard, the study of anthroponyms, which have a special place in the system of onomastic units, is also important as a linguistic resource that reflects the specific characteristics of the people's lifestyle, social, economic, cultural and educational relations in the national language.

In world linguistics, nomenclature is becoming more and more theoretical and practical as an important direction in the nomenclature of linguistics. Literary onomastics, i.e. identification of personal names in literary texts, their gender genesis, etymological characteristics, national traditions and values, customs, lifestyle, religious worldview, artistic and cultural wealth of the population using these names, are especially among the onomastic trends. special attention is paid to studying on the basis of the works that reflect the information about the people, revealing the linguistic, cultural, paradigmatic, onomastic-grammatical signs of the anthroponyms, which embody the linguistic, historical, geographical, ethnographic, religious-mythological views of the people.

At a time when in our country it is considered that "in today's era of globalization, it is natural for every independent country to give priority to the issue of ensuring its national interest, and in this regard, first of all, to the preservation and development of its culture, ancient values, and mother tongue."¹⁵ Collecting and studying the names of people who have the ability to reflect the national mentality and are related to linguistic descriptions of language and cultural phenomena is also relevant. After all, anthroponyms describe the development of cultural and historical life, as well as the national value system of a people who own a certain language. There is a need to develop the scientific principles of historical and modern names in the Uzbek language, onomastic lexicography (onomastic lexicography), to preserve the nationality and naturalness of famous names in the field, and to determine the compatibility of the name with the laws of the national language.

In the early 60s of the last century, onomastics became one of the most actively studied branches of linguistics. In the process of scientific research, the object and subject of research were determined, and now the field of researching the methodical

¹⁵ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and position of the Uzbek language as a state language" PF –5850. October 21, 2019. www.lex.uz

application of the science of onomastics is actively developing. After all, onomastics is a science related to a number of other linguistic sciences, including sociolinguistics, onomasiology, text linguistics, stylistics, and communicative linguistics.

Russian and foreign scientists have been interested in onomastics for many years. Onomastics began to develop as an independent branch of linguistics from the second half of the 20th century. At the first international onomastic congress held in France in 1930, it was officially declared an independent science and field. After all, if we take into account that scientific and theoretical gatherings and special trainings dedicated to onomastics were organized in many countries before this, we know that this is not the year of the emergence of onomastics, but the year of its recognition by world science. .

In 1949, an onomastic committee was established under UNESCO, and the "Onoma" magazine was published. At the same time, the magazine "Revue internationale d'onomastique" was established in Paris. In 1955, a magazine called "Onomastica" [Shmelyova, 2013] began to be published in Poland. At the same time, the XIII international congress on onomastics was held in Poland in August 1978.¹⁶

Anthroponyms, which are part of the lexical system of the Uzbek language, form another unique structure. These are:

1. Names: Kumush, Feruza, Dilshod, Alisher.
2. Nicknames: leper, deaf, lame.
3. Nicknames: Navoiy, Gulxaniy, Julqunboy.
4. Surnames: Saidnosirova, Qahhorova, Mo'minova.
5. Patronymic names: Rasulovna, Nusratovich, Axtam o'g'li.
6. Conditional names: Bahrom-Baxi, Shohruh-Shoxi.¹⁷

¹⁶ Осипова Н. Ономастика как отрасль лингвистических исследований // <http://jurnal.org/articles/2017/fill1.html>.

¹⁷ Қиличев Э. Айний асарларида антропонимларнинг стилистик хусусиятлари // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти, 1978,4.

In the period after the 60s of the 20th century, the research of the system of proper nouns in the Uzbek language in modern linguistic methods increased. In particular, as mentioned above, many scientific articles and dissertations were written on the names of places, names of people and other fields. Despite this, the ongoing work on Uzbek linguistics cannot be considered sufficient and satisfactory. Because there are a lot of nouns in the Uzbek language, it is necessary to collect all their forms and study their historical development (1); the scientific principles of nomenclature (onomastic lexicography) of ancient names in the Uzbek language have not been developed (2); materials of historical names have not been studied to date (3); In almost all the works on Uzbek names, the features of the names are analyzed. But these observations are not related to the practical problems of nomenclature. In particular, insufficient opinion is expressed about the pronunciation, spelling, and stylistic use of personal names (4). The successful solution of the important theoretical and practical problems of names in the Uzbek language is largely related to the thorough study of the historical development of these names. This idea applies equally to all types and groups of names in the Uzbek language. Methodical meanings, place and uniqueness of anthroponyms in the text of an artistic work have not been studied and a comparative analysis has not been carried out (5).

Some of the anthroponyms are full-fledged anthroponymic appropriations, and the other part are names created in the Uzbek language, created by Uzbeks, and it is not correct to include them among the appropriations. Failure to distinguish this leads to artificially increasing and exaggerating the number of appropriated names in the Uzbek language. Also common anthroponymic types of anthroponyms are found in our language. Examples of common troponyms in our language are Barno, Shamshad, Izzat, Nazar, which are given to both men and women. We consider it appropriate to call such names generic names.

Among the current problems of Uzbek nomenclature, the study of nicknames and nicknames has a special place. Because the more we turn to ancient times, the difference between names and nicknames decreases, and the role of nicknames as a means of naming in general increases. In general, it is not enough to study nicknames and nicknames only as a nominative tool, but it is also important to study them as an artistic and stylistic tool. In such observations, it is important to reveal commonalities and mutual differences between names, nicknames and nicknames.

It is known that the fund of Turkic names is a common property for many (historical) Turkic peoples. However, these names are not preserved to the same extent in all Turkic languages, and the existing ones have their own aspects according to their meaning and linguistic form. Therefore, the fund of Turkic names, on the one hand, creates a sign of commonality in the anthroponymy of sister Turkic languages, and on the other hand, provides uniqueness and nationalism in the set of names of each language. In this sense, it is very important to compare the original Turkish names in the modern Uzbek language with the fund of ancient Turkish names, and through this, to determine the national identity in Uzbek anthroponymy and to determine its main linguistic signs.

REFERENCES

1. Hamroyeva, R. M. (2021). Application of Anthroponymic Units in the Works of Tahir Malik (On The Example of the Story" Devona"). *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 8.
2. Rasulovna, H. M. (2021). Use Of Anthroponyms In Tahir Malik's Stories. *Journal of Contemporary*.
3. Rasulovna, H. M. (2021). Anthroponymic forms in the text of artistic work (On the example of Tahir Malik's work). *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 10.
4. Rasulovna, H. M. THE LITERARY OF ANTHROPONYMS. *Chief Editor*.

5. Rasulovna, H. M. (2022). TOHIR MALIKNING ASARLARIDA ONOMASTIK BIRLIKLAR QOLLANILISHINING USLUBIY TAHLILI. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(4), 391-398.
6. HAMROYEVA, M. (2021). BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUV. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).
7. Ahmedov, A. R. (2022). Some Feedback About Linguistic Knowledge. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(5), 125-131.
8. Raxmatovich, A. A., & Rasulovna, H. M. (2022). BADIY ASAR ANTROPONIMLARIDA LUGAVIY QATLAM MASALALARI (TOHIR MALIKNING IJODI MISOLIDA). *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(4), 399-402.
9. Akhmedov, A. R., & qizi Po'latova, S. M. (2021, December). O'zbek shevalarini lingvo-geografik xaritalashtirish. In *Conferences*.
10. Akhmedov, A. R. (2021). AREALOGIYA TUSHUNCHASI HAQIDA: Atouullo Rakhmatovich Akhmedov Buxoro davlat universiteti dotsenti Buxoro, O'zbekiston ar ahmedov@buxdu.uz Sevara Mahmud qizi Po'latova Buxoro davlat universiteti o'qituvchisi Buxoro, O'zbekiston E-mail: sevaramahmudqizi@gmail.ru. In *Научно-практическая конференция*.
11. Rahmatovich, A. A. VOBKENT TUMANI SHEVASIDA SO'ZNING MORFEMIK TARKIBI. *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY*, 123.